

Roundtable

Introduction: The More (and Sometimes More Important) Ideas That Made America Roundtable

BY MICHAEL J. KRAMER | FEBRUARY 10, 2025

Introducing the inaugural roundtable for *The Carryall*.

It is no small thing to write a small thing.

Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagen has written the first survey of US intellectual history since the mid-twentieth century. She has written it as a brief text. The book is at once sweeping and sweeps a lot under the rug. Through what Ratner-Rosenhagen calls “voice and vision” she tries to navigate oceans of thought by way of a little speedboat. Come onboard, she announces to students and newcomers, you’ll like what you find, even if we just skim the surface as I race through expansive waters.

It is a noble effort, and, as our roundtable shows, it is successful on many levels. Most of all, as a brief survey, *The Ideas That Made America* offers an opportunity to think more deeply and broadly about US intellectual history.

In the inaugural roundtable for *The Carryall*, we have asked a diverse set of scholars not so much to review *The Ideas That Made America*, but rather to use it as a starting point, a launch pad, a generator; or as a foil, an antipode, a tide, something they wish to oppose by offering a different focus or tale of US intellectual history. Use what metaphor you wish, but the roundtable seeks to expand upon Ratner-Rosenhagen’s brief history by offering “More (And Sometimes More Important) Ideas That Made America.”

We hope the results from over 15 scholars will let scholars, teachers, students, and interested citizens delve further into the rich range of US intellectual history in its

contemporary state. One can pair these essays with the book in a course or read them along with Ratner-Rosenhagen’s text on your own. Or just read each essays in its own right, as an independent work of scholarship and commentary. However one approaches the roundtable, here is no breezy story through the ideas that made America, but that is how it should be. There are stronger currents to learn to navigate these days.

“More (And Sometimes More Important) Ideas That Made America” will move sequentially through Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagen’s book over the coming weeks. We are delighted to publish these essays at *The Carryall*.

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...criticism has been the great American lay philosophy, the intellectual conscience and the intellectual carryall. — Alfred Kazin

